

Road to the Future: The Impact of Road Infrastructure on Education in Colombia

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Summary

1. This study demonstrates that infrastructure investments have the potential to significantly enhance educational outcomes.
2. Road projects in Colombia led to a 3% decrease in child labour and a 4.8% increase in the number of students pursuing higher education, highlighting their role in fostering human capital development.
3. Even partial road completion (as early as 10%) begins to positively affect students' academic performance, suggesting that benefits emerge progressively throughout construction.
4. The findings provide evidence that infrastructure development, when well-targeted, contributes not only to economic growth but also to social mobility and educational equity, especially in underserved rural areas.

1. Introduction

Ensuring equitable access to quality education remains a central priority for the European Union, both within its borders and in its cooperation with partner countries. In many developing regions, however, physical barriers—particularly poor road infrastructure—continue to hinder educational progress, especially in rural areas. This policy brief summarizes findings from a study that examines Colombia's large-scale Public-Private Partnership (PPP) road

concession program. It provides robust evidence on how improving road connectivity directly impacts student test scores, child labour, and long-term educational aspirations, offering critical lessons for policymakers seeking to leverage infrastructure for social and human development. The evidence highlights how targeted infrastructure investment can yield substantial returns in human capital formation, including reductions in child labour and increased participation in higher education. These findings are highly relevant for EU development policy and cohesion

strategies, which increasingly emphasise the role of infrastructure in promoting inclusive, sustainable growth and reducing regional inequalities—both within the EU and in its external partnerships.

2. Data and Methodology

The analysis uses comprehensive student-level data from Colombia's national standardized test (SABER 11) for the years 2006-2021. This academic data was linked with detailed, georeferenced information on the location, timing, and progress of national road construction projects managed through PPPs. The study focuses on schools located within a 1.5 km radius of these road projects to isolate the localized impact of improved accessibility.

To establish a causal link, the study employs a robust staggered difference-in-differences approach (Sun & Abraham, 2021). This method compares educational outcomes in schools near road projects before and after construction, relative to a control group of schools further away. Crucially, the analysis examines the impact at different stages of project completion (e.g., 10%, 50%, and 100%), which allows for a dynamic understanding of how the effects evolve from the disruptive construction phase to the beneficial operational phase.

3. Results

Four key findings emerge from the analysis:

First, the impact of road construction is dynamic and evolves over time. The study shows that the short-term disruptions of construction are real, but they are followed by substantial long-term benefits. As illustrated in Figure 1 and Figure 2, there is an initial negative effect on student math scores at the

start of construction, likely due to noise, traffic, and other disruptions. As the project progresses, this negative effect disappears, and upon completion, it transforms into a strong, positive impact on student learning.

Second, completed roads significantly boost academic achievement. Upon full completion (100%), road projects lead to meaningful gains in student learning. Math scores increase by a substantial **0.169 standard deviations**, and reading scores also show a significant improvement of **0.112 standard deviations**.

Third, improved infrastructure encourages higher educational aspirations. The benefits of new roads extend beyond secondary school. The study finds a **4.8 percentage point increase** in the proportion of students who pursue higher education after the roads are completed. This suggests that improved connectivity to urban centres and new economic opportunities broadens students' horizons and motivates them to invest in their human capital.

Fourth, better roads help reduce child labour. The study reveals a dynamic relationship between roads and child labour... In the long term, completed roads are associated with a **3.2 percentage point decrease** in child labour participation. This suggests that improved connectivity creates new economic opportunities for adults, reducing families' reliance on child income—a mechanism consistent with broader research on the economic impacts of rural roads (Asher & Novosad, 2020).

4. Policy Recommendations

These findings offer clear, actionable insights for governments and development partners:

1. Manage Expectations and Communicate the Long-Term Vision. Policymakers and project managers should anticipate a temporary dip in educational performance and a potential rise in child labour during the disruptive construction phase. It is critical to communicate to communities, schools, and local leaders that these are expected, short-term effects. This prevents premature negative evaluations of the project and builds trust by showing that the substantial, long-term educational and economic benefits are the ultimate goal.

3. Prioritise Connectivity for Marginalised Communities.

EU regional development funds should continue to prioritise connectivity improvements in remote, rural, or disadvantaged areas. As the Colombian case shows, proximity to high-quality roads is a key enabler of educational opportunity. Investing in transport networks that link peripheral areas to educational institutions can reduce dropout rates, improve learning outcomes, and promote long-term socioeconomic mobility.

4. Adopt a Long-Term Perspective in Project Evaluation. The full educational benefits of road infrastructure only materialize after a project is complete. Cost-benefit analyses and project evaluations must account for these significant, long-term positive externalities on education and human capital, which traditional models may overlook.

5. Promote Evidence-Based Policymaking and Data Integration.

European regions should be encouraged to collect and link infrastructure, education, and labour market data to assess the full social return of transport investments. This integrated approach supports smarter, more

targeted policymaking and aligns with EU efforts to strengthen evidence-based decision-making under the European Semester and Cohesion Policy frameworks.

What is BRIDGE ?

BRIDGE is an impact-driven project that aims to build resilient individuals through effective educational transition by formulating robust policy recommendations on education and training policies, the efficient use of public resources and the support of equity and inclusion in education and training systems in the EU.

References

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Figures

Figure 1: Impact on Math Scores Increases After Road is Completed. The graph shows effect for math scores across distance bands and construction stages.

Figure 2: Impact on Reading Literacy Scores Increases After Road is Completed. The graph shows effect for reading literacy scores across distance bands and construction stages.

Further Information:

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